

OPPORTUNITIES FOR JOINT BIO-BASED MARKETING OF FARMERS FROM SMOLYAN DISTRICT, BULGARIA

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Abstract

Access to profitable markets is perhaps the single most influential factor in determining the viability of the agricultural sector. It is a crucial factor for small farms which have historically had limited access to viable and profitable markets, usually marketing their products right out of the field through peddling and individual sales. These weaknesses of business can be overcome through participation in cooperative marketing.

The aim of the article is to determine benefits and constraints of joint – marketing in farms from Smolyan district.

Farmers can achieve three types of benefits from participation in joint marketing - 1) better market information; 2) access to profitable market; 3) higher profit. These benefits are considered as results of direct contact with consumers. There will not be used external intermediaries. Some constraints restrain farmers to participate in forms of cooperative marketing. Farmers have doubts about management of the process and coordination between independent farmers.

Key words: business model, small farms, risk, joint marketing, bio-based marketing

Abstrakt

Der Zugang zu profitablen Märkten ist vielleicht der einflussreichste Einzelfaktor, der die Lebensfähigkeit des Agrarsektors bestimmt. Er ist ein entscheidender Faktor für kleine Betriebe, die in der Vergangenheit nur begrenzten Zugang zu lebensfähigen und rentablen Märkten hatten und ihre Produkte in der Regel direkt vom Feld aus durch Hausieren und Einzelverkäufe vermarkten. Diese Schwächen des Geschäfts können durch die Teilnahme an der genossenschaftlichen Vermarktung überwunden werden.

Ziel des Artikels ist es, die Vorteile und Zwänge der genossenschaftlichen Vermarktung in landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben aus dem Distrikt Smolyan zu ermitteln.

Die Landwirte können durch die Teilnahme am genossenschaftlichen Marketing drei Arten von Vorteilen erzielen - 1) bessere Marktinformationen; 2) Zugang zu einem profitablen Markt; 3) höherer Gewinn. Diese Vorteile werden als Ergebnisse des direkten Kontakts mit den Verbrauchern betrachtet. Es werden keine externen Vermittler eingesetzt. Einige Einschränkungen schränken die Teilnahme der Landwirte an Formen der genossenschaftlichen Vermarktung ein. Die Landwirte haben Zweifel am Management des Prozesses und an der Koordination zwischen unabhängigen Landwirten.

Schlüsselwörter: Geschäftsmodell, Kleinbetriebe, Risiko, gemeinsame Vermarktung, biobasierte Vermarktung

Résumé

L'accès à des marchés rentables est peut-être le facteur le plus influent pour déterminer la viabilité du secteur agricole. C'est un facteur crucial pour les petites exploitations agricoles qui ont historiquement eu un accès limité à des marchés viables et rentables, commercialisant généralement leurs produits dès la sortie des champs par le biais du colportage et des ventes individuelles. Ces faiblesses commerciales peuvent être surmontées par la participation à des coopératives de commercialisation.

L'objectif de cet article est de déterminer les avantages et les contraintes de la commercialisation coopérative dans les exploitations agricoles du district de Smolyan.

Les agriculteurs peuvent tirer trois types d'avantages de la participation au marketing coopératif: 1) une meilleure information sur le marché; 2) l'accès à un marché rentable; 3) des bénéfices plus élevés. Ces avantages sont considérés comme le résultat d'un contact direct avec les consommateurs. Il ne sera pas fait appel à des intermédiaires externes. Certaines contraintes empêchent les agriculteurs de participer à des formes de commercialisation coopérative. Les agriculteurs ont des doutes quant à la gestion du processus et à la coordination entre les agriculteurs indépendants.

Mots clés: modèle d'entreprise, petites exploitations, risque, commercialisation conjointe, commercialisation fondée sur la biologie

Introduction

Bulgarian farmers face serious difficulties in carrying out their business in today's dynamic business environment. They often make decisions without having the complete information on the cost of production factors, the opportunities for financial support, the characteristics of market demand, the risks accompanying their activity, return on invested capital, etc. Information about these components and their integration in agricultural production systems is necessary to improve the profitability and viability of farms.

Access to market is among the most important factors affecting production activity. It is a key factor particularly for small farms, which are difficult to resist competition and find market for their products. Most often these stopnastva rely on individual sales. This way of offering takes place at prices that do not correspond to production costs in order to achieve the desired profitability. Profitability is a prerequisite to enable the business to continue its existence and its improvement requires careful planning of resources and activities on farms.

The aim of the article is to determine benefits and constraints of joint bio-based marketing in farms from Smolyan district.

Joint Bio-based marketing

Joint bio-based marketing is any agreement between farmers to combine marketing efforts, which may occur in a variety of forms (Borisov, 2013). Bio-based marketing is approach for business management relying on the idea to use environmentally friendly methods of organizing of business activities of any business model in value chain (Stoeva and Vulcheva, 2016). In a bio-based marketing, biologically derived materials will replace synthetic materials in marketing of agricultural and food products (Sijtsema, 2016).

Also any approach for cutting down the plastic waste in production and promotion of food can be formulated as bio-based marketing (Praus and Boevsky, 2015).

Small-sized farms can perform useful and efficient joint marketing campaigns. Sharing resources and ideas is an important part of the collaboration. For example, a group of producers in a region can rent designer of websites that presented their products to their target customers. Joint activity is often targeted at sales by making a larger market penetration (Yovchevska, 2015.). Thus farmers obtain greater market strength and have the ability to influence the pricing process for obtaining a higher price for their products. Another popular form of joint bio-based marketing promotion is reference to fellow farmer. In practice this means a farmer to promote its client's products of another farmer who complement his business activities. In carrying out joint marketing place to implement one or more of the following goals - improving the economic efficiency; sharing resources; better market performance; access to a market; convincing consumers (Kolaj and Borisov, 2019). For small farms, joint marketing activities can be a powerful tool for maintenance and development of their business (Nedeva and Marinov, 2015). To realize that approach, farmers must be involved in a variety of arrangements for mutually beneficial activities.

Results

To study rely on information received from 30 farmers from Smolyan District. Their production activity is focused on the cultivation of beans, potatoes and sheep-breeding that are typical for the region, and produces agricultural products formed almost exclusively agricultural incomes and have built an image of the region. Appropriate conditions for production and traditions in these proceedings are popular among the local community, while consumers evaluate products manufactured here as quality and natural.

Figure 1. Farmers membership in professional association. Source: Own survey, 2019

Agriculture in the region is small and fragmented, which is typical for mountain regions. The small size of production puts farmers at a disadvantage to suppliers and intermediaries, and the presence of multiple farms makes it difficult to control. Under these conditions, participation in associations of producers may enable optimal use of resources and facilitate activities through mutual support and coordination. In the inquiry set experience very small number of farmers who are members of an agricultural association. Only 7% (Fig.1) said they were active members of the association and seek advantage based on mutual interest such as farmers and solve similar problems. Interest in participating

in agricultural associations is very low, but it is explained by the fact that farmers do not recognize the association as an effective structure to solve their problems.

Farmers use two basic channels (often in combination) for the realization of its products – Direct sales (in place) and retail (Fig. 2). Do not look for marketplaces and do not enter into contracts with processors because the volumes produced are small and these forms of marketing of produce are not suitable.

Figure 2. Sales channels. Source: Own survey, 2019

Already it mentioned that the region has suitable conditions for development of agricultural production set - beans, potatoes and sheep-breeding. However, nearly one third of respondents define the image of these products as a weak or absent (Fig. 3), which is surprising against the background of the positive user review. Yet no small part by the farmers appreciate the image of local products as high, which enables to produce products with clear identification of origin. This is evidenced by the willingness of all respondents to participate in forms of joint marketing for the production and marketing of products with a registered origin (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. Image of the local products. Source: Own survey, 2019

Figure 4. Willingness to participate in joint marketing association. Source: Own survey, 2019

Participation in joint marketing association can result in a variety of benefits for farmers. These benefits can be grouped into two main areas - improving the integration of farms in the food chain and improve business. In terms of improved integration (Fig. 5), farmers in the region expect the joint marketing to provide them with direct contact with end users, where they will not need external mediators. This will enable them to be aware of consumer demands on the one hand and on the other to be able to position their products by focusing on their specific characteristics and present the advantages of its business and region. This can be achieved by offering local products with guaranteed origin. Interesting is the fact that the majority of respondents believe that joint marketing would not lead to improved quality of products offered.

Figure 5. Effect of joint marketing on the integration of the economy in the Food Chain. Source: Own survey, 2019

This explains the problems of local farmers are not related to product quality, but rather to ensure its users. The clear product identification products from the region will provide precisely such a benefit. The majority of respondents do not see an opportunity to diversify the product range as a result of the

introduction of joint marketing. This is due to the limited production capacity of the region as natural and climatic conditions are specific and provide an opportunity to grow a limited number of crops. However, the image of the region in these proceedings can be used to expand their marketing. The majority of respondents do not see an opportunity to diversify the product range as a result of the introduction of joint marketing. This is due to the limited production capacity of the region as natural and climatic conditions are specific and provide an opportunity to grow a limited number of crops. However, the image of the region in these proceedings can be used to expand their marketing. The majority of respondents do not see an opportunity to diversify the product range as a result of the introduction of joint marketing. This is due to the limited production capacity of the region as natural and climatic conditions are specific and provide an opportunity to grow a limited number of crops. However, the image of the region in these proceedings can be used to expand their marketing.

Joint marketing can affect the economic activities of farmers who participate in this form of association. As main benefits are recognized three - 1) better awareness of market requirements; 2) facilitating market access; 3) realization of higher operating profit (Fig. 6). Also, the majority of respondents believe that joint marketing would give them the opportunity to diversify their sources of income. But it will be implemented in the context of increasing the share of income from agricultural activity in the total income, as is currently the share is unsatisfactory. It is also stated that it expected contribution of joint marketing on a more efficient use of available resources and improve the quality of the implemented production activities.

Figure 6. Effect of joint marketing on business. Source: Own survey, 2019

Participation in joint marketing association is possible only if there are certain incentives to motivate farmers to whitewash part of such unification. The problems faced by small farmers are diverse, but these market-related definitely have a critical impact on their business (Nikolov et al., 2015). This is confirmed by the answers of respondents that facilitating access to the market, in close contact and direct communication with end users and the ability to successfully resist the competitive pressures are among the main reasons to participate in joint marketing (Fig.7). Also has estimated costs related to the implementation of production to be reduced since this management process will be optimized. It is noteworthy that farmers do not recognize the benefits associated with easier access to financial

resources. This is because the small size of the business opportunity sets its own funds to cover the cost, which is often the main income of the farmers come from other activities used to finance the cost of farming.

Figure 7. What motivates farmers to participate in joint marketing. Source: Own survey, 2019

Participation in joint marketing discourage some limitations that cast doubt on its successful functioning as a form of association. Respondents rated 6 potential factors that deterred them to participate in joint marketing. The evaluation was performed by four-point scale, with a higher score indicating a strong deterrent role of this factor. The sum of the scores of all respondents determines the overall score for each factor, the maximum value is 90 points. Six constraints were identified as potential disincentives, and the results show that all of them have a very strong restrictive effects (Fig. 8). The most significant factor among them is determined reluctance to association of farmers due to lack of mutual trust. Reporting of such high marks for all six factors.

Figure 8. What discourages farmers to participate in joint marketing. Source: Own survey, 2019

Conclusion

The implementation of agricultural activity is carried out under conditions of uncertainty and risk as factors of the business environment have dominant importance. This is especially true for farmers in

mountainous areas whose farms are characterized by small size and are located in areas that are disadvantaged in terms of natural and climatic conditions. This creates difficulties for the effective functioning of farms achieve their financial and economic objectives and maintain their viability in the long term. Farmers of these areas difficult to compete with manufacturers from other regions, which need to explore new approaches in the management of production and supply of agricultural products. Joint marketing is an opportunity to organize production activity and distribution of finished products through cooperation among farmers. The cooperation allows for better use of available resources, to increase the efficiency of operations. Farmers can coordinate their actions in terms of production output by offering the market a wide range and in larger quantities. Meanwhile local associations can utilize the advantages of the region in which they operate by offering their products with clear product identification of origin and guarantees. This will allow products to position themselves with their own unique qualities that distinguish them from those of other manufacturers. Thus it can overcome the mass nature of the product and to serve specific segments of the market for agricultural products that do not show such a strong price sensitivity as well as the general public. Implementation of joint marketing has its challenges that impede its implementation and effective use. The main restrictions are related to the effectiveness of the management processes and coordinating the activities of various entities.

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